

REDUCTION OF COPPER BORATE BY HYDROGEN

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Reduction of crystalline copper borate, $\text{CuO} \cdot \text{B}_2\text{O}_3$, by hydrogen follows the course: $\text{CuO} \cdot \text{B}_2\text{O}_3 + \text{H}_2 = \text{Cu} + \text{B}_2\text{O}_3 + \text{H}_2\text{O}$. In the temperature range of 500° to 750° , the reduction is fairly rapid and goes to completion in about 30 minutes at 750° . The reduction process is probably accompanied with the phenomenon of activated adsorption.

Copper oxide is known to be easily reduced by carbon. Tammann and Zvoruikin (*Z. anorg. allg. Chem.*, 1928, 170, 67) found 700° and 790° as starting points in the reduction of cupric oxide by sugar charcoal and graphite respectively. Khundkar (this *Journal*, 1952, 29, 467) studied the reduction of copper oxide by carbon in presence of B_2O_3 and $\text{Na}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7$ melts in the temperature range of 600° - 750° , in which these melts themselves were inert towards carbon. It was observed that in the absence of carbon, copper oxide combined with B_2O_3 to form a borate (a new, but unidentified X-ray diffraction pattern), which was later reduced by carbon to metallic copper, through the intermediate formation of Cu_2O . In continuation of that work, we report here a study of the reduction of pure crystalline copper borate by hydrogen.

EXPERIMENTAL

The crystalline copper borate was prepared by heating an intimate mixture of CuS and $\text{Na}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7$ (in the molar ratio of 1 : 1) in a platinum crucible at 900° for about 2 hours in presence of air. Blue, needle-shaped crystals of copper borate, so obtained, was purified from the reaction product by treatment with HCl (conc.) in which the crystalline borate remained insoluble. It was finally washed thoroughly with water and dried. On determination of copper and borate (Haider and Rahim, *Pakistan J. Sci. Res.*, 1952, 4, 65) it was found to conform to the composition, $\text{CuO} \cdot \text{B}_2\text{O}_3$. (Found: Cu, 42.25, 42.90; B, 14.45, 14.45. Calc. for $\text{CuO} \cdot \text{B}_2\text{O}_3$: Cu, 42.60; B, 14.50 per cent).

The apparatus used for studying the reduction was more or less the same as that described by Khundkar (this *Journal*, 1952, 29, 341) but the right hand side of the main system was connected to a gas circulating pump instead of the CO-CO_2 determination train. By this set up, it was possible to start the reaction in an atmosphere of hydrogen and follow the progress of reduction from the decrease in gas volume at different intervals of time. The water vapour formed during the reaction was absorbed in P_2O_5 , taken in a boat and placed in the exit (cooler) end of the reaction tube. The gas circulating system ensured uniform circulation of gas throughout the entire reaction system. Reactions were carried out in a small platinum boat.

Analysis of the Product.—Interpretation of the results was based on the analysis of the solid products of reaction. The procedure of analysis is schematically outlined below:

Separate experiments were carried out at different temperatures in the range 500° to 750° . In order to compare the results better, the same amount of reactant (viz. 0.25 g.) was taken in each case. The total volumes of gas adsorbed (corrected to N.T.P.) at different intervals of time have been plotted in Fig. 1. At 600° the adsorption of hydrogen has a short induction period. Between 500° and 700° , the decrease in the volume of hydrogen is extremely rapid during the first ten minutes. After this, the adsorption (reduction) proceeds very slowly and comes to a steady state in about two hour's time.

FIG. 1

The theoretical amount of hydrogen required for complete reduction to copper (without affecting the B_2O_3) is 37.5 c.c. It is thus clear that either the B_2O_3 has been

partially reduced or the reduction process is associated with adsorption of gas in excess of that required for reduction. The free energy of formation of B_2O_3 ($-\Delta G$) is considerably high; and also from available literature, it appears improbable that B_2O_3 will be reduced to boron at such low temperatures. The question of adsorption will be discussed in a later section.

Extent of Reduction at different Temperatures.—It was observed that in the products of reduction there was, at all temperatures, an amount of free boric oxide that could be extracted with water. It seems probable that the borate is reduced to metallic copper and boric oxide is released. A similar reaction was observed in the case of zinc silicate reduction by Kitchener and Ignatowicz (*Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1951, 47, 1278):

In the case of copper borate, however, the reduction may proceed directly as in (i) or through the intermediate formation of a cuprous borate, as in (ii) below:

Existence of a yellow cuprous borate has been mentioned (Mellor, "Comprehensive Treatise in Inorganic and Theoretical Chemistry", Vol. V, p. 84, Longmans, 1924), but, nothing is known definitely about its composition or properties. If the cuprous borate is insoluble in strong nitric acid, it would contaminate the final residue (vide scheme of analysis); but in all cases it has been found that the unchanged residue after treatment with nitric acid is a perfectly blue crystalline mass (except for reaction at 750° , where nothing is left behind). It is probable that the cuprous borate could have been soluble in strong acid and thus extracted with metallic copper. But in such extracts, no test for boric acid was found, indicating that there was no intermediate formation of cuprous borate as a stable phase. A final evidence is to be obtained from results in Table I.

TABLE I

Analysis of products of reduction of copper borate by hydrogen at different temperatures.

$CuO \cdot B_2O_3$ taken = 0.25 g. (corresponds to 0.1065 g. Cu and 0.1168 g. B_2O_3).

Temp.	Reduction Period.	B_2O_3 in water extract.		Cu in acid extract.		Mean value of reduction.
500°	180 mins.	0.0760 g.	65.1 %	0.0693 g.	65.1 g.	65.1 %
550°	120	0.0853	73.0	0.0777	73.0	73.0
600°	90	0.0971	83.1	0.0900	84.5	83.8
650°	90	0.1015	86.9	0.0927	87.1	87.0
700°	45	0.1075	92.0	0.1007	94.6	93.3
750°	30	0.1150	98.5	0.1064	99.9	99.2

The amount of free boric acid was determined in the product of each experiment and expressed in terms of percentage of total B_2O_3 input (as copper borate). Also the copper obtained in the acid extract was expressed in terms of percentage of total copper input. A close resemblance of the two sets of results also indicates that the reduction

proceeds directly to the formation of metallic copper according to equation (i), above. The mean of the two values has been taken as the extent of reduction at a particular temperature. The period of reduction was not, however, the same in each case. Instead, at each temperature, the reduction was continued till it was so slow that not more than 1.0 c.c. of hydrogen was adsorbed in one hour. At 500°, the reduction is fairly high, 65.1%. It increases steadily with increase of temperature. The progress of reaction (percentage reduction) can be represented by the reaction,

$$Y = 0.1364 t - 31,$$

where Y is the percentage conversion to metallic copper, and t is the temperature in degrees centigrade.

Phenomenon of Adsorption.—In Table II, a set of results is presented (column 3) for the theoretical amounts of hydrogen required for reduction, as calculated from the mean value of the extent of reduction. This has been compared with the actual values of hydrogen adsorbed (obtained from the curves in Fig. 1).

TABLE II

Adsorption of hydrogen at different temperatures in the reduction of copper borate.
CuO.B₂O₃ in each experiment = 0.25 g.

Temp.	Reduction Mean value.	* Vol. of H ₂ reacted.	Actual vol. (total) of H ₂ adsorbed.	Vol. of H ₂ adsorbed in excess.
500°	65.1 %	24.5 c.c.	24.2 c.c.	- 0.3 c.c.
550°	73.0	27.4	39.2	+11.8
600°	83.8	31.3	51.2	+19.9
650°	87.0	32.7	53.5	+20.8
700°	93.3	35.0	54.6	+19.6
750°	99.2	37.2	59.0	+21.8

* As computed from column 2.

At 500°, there is no excess of hydrogen adsorbed over that required for reduction. The difference between the total hydrogen adsorbed and that reacted (called excess hydrogen) increases with increase of temperature and appears to reach a limiting value. The adsorption resembles the "activated adsorption" observed in the case of manganese and chromic oxides by Taylor *et al.* (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 53, 2168). But a fundamental difference is that the present case is complicated by the simultaneous reduction of borate. The limiting value of the excess hydrogen adsorbed (600°-750°) can be taken to be approximately 20 c.c., corresponding to 0.88 mg. mole (or 1.76 mg. atom). The amount of CuO.B₂O₃ taken (0.25 g.) was 1.68 mg. mole. It thus appears that the adsorption probably tends to a saturation value of one atom of hydrogen for each molecule of CuO.B₂O₃ taken or B₂O₃ formed.

The idea of activated adsorption is not, however, conclusively established. Because there is a possibility that some hydrogen might have been consumed in the reduction of B₂O₃ to some unstable suboxides of boron, formation of which (or otherwise) could not be definitely proved.